

**An Investigation into the Effect of Social Media Addiction on Library Users of Bayelsa State
Polytechnic, Aleibiri**

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Abstract

The study discussed the effects of social media addiction on library users of the Bayelsa State Polytechnic, Aleibiri. It defined and explained social media addiction, and the different themes relating to social media addiction. The study had five objectives and research questions. The literature reviewed social media as a concept, the benefits of using social media and addictions, the types of addiction consequences of social media addiction, and suggestions on ways to reduce social media addiction. A descriptive survey design was used for the study. The population for the study is 100, while the sample size was 48. A purposive sampling technique was used to select the sample. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data and Chi Square and descriptive analysis was used to analyse the results. The study concluded that social media is beneficial to library users but with potential for abuse by library users with dire consequences in terms of their physical and mental health, and academic performance. The study suggests ways of managing social media addiction through acknowledging their addiction, reviewing past posts, setting priorities right, turning off all notifications, avoid posting everyday life experiences, limiting their social media usage and transfer their social media account to another people.

Keyword: Addiction, social media, library users, Bayelsa State

Introduction

The use of social media has increased in the last decade with billions using it according to Statista (2020). Since its inception, the reach and penetration of social platforms has been in geometric proportions within the business, civil, government, and individual circles (Odigie et al., 2022). This is due to the global technological revolution which has led to increased traffic on the internet by users for different reasons (Alqudah et al, 2020). Hruska and Maresova (2020) opined that the Internet-connected mobile devices have changed the use of mobile devices including social media. Although the use of social media in itself is not problematic, however, it has potential for unhealthy usage, and many users have become addicted to the use of social media. Social media addiction is an unhealthy dependence on interaction platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, Tiktok, and Snapchat (Spencer, 2020). Like most dependences, social media addiction manifests as overuse and having a difficulty in abstaining from it, which sometimes leads to social isolation (Ahmed, 2023). It is also a behavioural addiction that is characterized as being overly concerned about social media, with an uncontrollable desire and devoting so much time and effort to social media, to the extent of impairing other important aspects of life.

Internet addiction includes cybersex addiction, net compulsion, cyber (online) relationships and compulsive information seeking. Fuhr (2018) states that internet addiction looks much like any substance use disorder, which may include mood modification, salience, withdrawal symptoms, conflict, and relapse. The phenomena of social media addiction can be largely attributed to the dopamine-inducing social environments that social media sites provide. As such social media sites like Facebook, Snapchat, Instagram, and WhatsApp for instance, produce the same neural circuitry that is caused by gambling or other recreational things to keep consumers coming back to use such products states the American Psychiatric Association (2013). Studies have shown that constant streams of retweets, likes and shares from these sites cause the brain's reward area to trigger the same kind of chemical reaction seen in drugs like cocaine. The continuous use can lead to multiple interpersonal problems such as ignoring real-life relationships, work or school responsibilities including physical health. Griffiths, 2000 noted that instead of engaging in academic activities, social media addicts spend much time on social media sites browsing and chatting, thus developing an addiction to specific activities they carry out online. Several scholars have described internet addiction (IA) as an impulse control disorder characterized by poorly controlled preoccupation, and urges that could lead to impairment or distress, as posited by Wang, Ren & Lory (2015).

Statement of the Problem

Social media is appealing to users because it is used presently in all aspects of life today. It occupies a significant place in our lives, we use it from our homes, and our mobile devices, etc. Many cannot do without the social media, it is used to send and receive mails through emails, communicate through the social media, carry out research, used to access news report, share ideas (Kenneth O. Irenea, 2021), entertain themselves, listen to music, watch films and play games. Its advantages are enormous, but it also has disadvantages that could pose a serious threat to Library users in the polytechnic due to over utilization. Caplan (2002) presented the theory of problematic internet use and psychosocial wellbeing, he stated that people who exhibited signs of poor psychosocial health experience a problematic relationship with the unique communicative context available in the internet. On the other hand, Davis (2001) in his cognitive-behavioural model of generalized problematic Internet use, explained the association between problematic Internet use and several psychological wellbeing variables, including self-esteem, loneliness, depression, and shyness. Other empirical studies revealed the relationship between excessive use of social media networks and health issues like withdrawal, isolation, addiction, depression, gambling, obesity, and anxiety among adults and teenagers. According to the social cognitive theory of Bandura (2001), His theory explains the relationship between beliefs and behaviour as a reciprocal learning process in which individuals select, react to and learn from experiences. The theory emphasizes how people can effectively learn through self-monitoring and self-guidance through personal standards and corrective self-reactions.

Studies by Ayeni (2019) states that internet addiction affects the academic achievement of students, a student said social media makes her feel inadequate about how much effort she is putting into her studies. She explains that during exam time her social media is full "friends showing how much they're revising." They sometimes feel depressed and lonely, tired and anxious due to too much use of social media during examination periods. Previous studies on internet addiction so far have focused on the role of parents, social media providers, and methods of controlling access and preventing social media addiction in adults and young users. In order to address the current shortcomings in the literature on social media addiction among Polytechnic Library users, this study intends to answer five key questions: "To what extent are the Bayelsa State Polytechnic library users addicted to social media?" "What are the most common social media activities the library users engage in?" "To what extent does gender influence social media Addiction among the Bayelsa State Polytechnic library users?" "How frequent do the library users engage in social media activities for a day?" "To what extent does the excessive social media use affect Bayelsa State Polytechnic Library users?" Results from this study will help researchers, lecturers, Librarians, Heads of Library Schools and social media platforms better understand the effect of Social Media addiction (SMA) to Library users in tertiary institutions.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the effect of social media addiction on library users of Bayelsa State Polytechnic, Aleibiri. The specific objectives are:

1. To find out the extent of social media addiction among the polytechnic library users in Bayelsa State Polytechnic, Aleibiri.
2. To find out the most common social media activities the library users engage in.
3. To know the extent gender influences social media Addiction among the Bayelsa State Polytechnic library users.
4. To determine the length of time spent on social media apps in a day.
5. To find out how excessive Social Media use affects library users in Bayelsa State Polytechnic, Aleibiri.

Research Questions

1. To what extent are the Bayelsa State Polytechnic library users addicted to social media?
2. What are the most common social media activities the library users engage in?
3. To what extent does gender influence social media Addiction among the Bayelsa State Polytechnic library users?
4. How frequent do the library users engage in social media activities for a day?
5. To what extent does the excessive social media use affect Bayelsa State Polytechnic Library users?"

Review of Related Literature

Addiction is a dependence, on a behaviour or substance that a person is powerless to stop” SNS addiction is defined by Andreassen and Pallesen (2014) as “being overly concerned about SNSs, to be driven by a strong motivation to log on to or use SNSs, and to devote so much time and effort to SNSs that it impairs other social activities, such as studies, job, interpersonal relationships, psychological health and well-being” Aslan & Yasar (2019) stated that If the answers to three or more questions below are “yes”, then one can be considered as a social media addict. • Spending a lot of time thinking about social media or planning to use social media? • Feeling urges to use social media more and more? • Using social media to forget about personal problems? • Often trying to reduce use of social media without success? • Becoming restless or troubled if unable to use social media? • Using social media so much that it has had a negative impact on job or studies? (Hilliard &Parisi, 2020) Social media addiction can be viewed as one form of Internet addiction, where individuals exhibit a compulsion to use social media to excess (Griffiths, 2000). There are five distinct types of social media use currently, and they are meeting or communicating with people, seeking information, an instrument of distraction, an instrument in coping and email (Edwards, 2017).

Many people stated they used social media to keep in touch with friends, chats, sharing interesting things, gathering useful information, decreasing emotional stress, spreading information, gaining more contacts, making groups, selling or buying products. Further expressing social media usage, (Irenea, 2017) states that participants create and share information through their interactions on topical issues and general happenings around them especially in trying to make sense of the happenings. Expression of opinions and relaxation are also reasons of usage, according Dalvi-Esfahani et al., (2019). (Baccarella, et al., 2018 stated that many firms in the EU use social media for marketing, public relations, customer service, product development, personnel decision-making etc. (Baccarella et al., 2018. According to (Wang, Lee, Hua, 2015: 40–49) Microblog pages are used for new tweets and followings, comments and retweets can make users happy. Microblogs can meet information-seeking and social connection of users. Gaining pleasant feelings and avoiding unpleasant feelings as a kind of intrinsic need like perceived enjoyment motivate users for social media while users do not focus on extrinsic utility (perceived usefulness), making perceived enjoyment a more crucial determinant of social media addiction, although both factors are used to explain adoption of technology such as SNS. From utility maximization to desired emotional states happens during that transition phase ending in irrational and emotional behaviour. (Wang, Lee, Hua, 2015) Mathematical analysis of experts on social networks shows that the probability of a person to be happy increases by 15% when a person distant is somewhat happy. Accordingly, the effect of happiness is 10% for a friend of a friend, and about 6% for people from three degrees and at four degrees away, the effect disappears (Tutgun-Ünal, 2015). Compulsive users lose track of time while they are online because they are carried away and more often cannot complete their necessary tasks, causing them to feel guilty, finding social media as a way of escape. Academic, family, and work lives can be ignored by the user in long term

that they over-rely on the utility and pleasure of microblogging meeting their internal needs that they are incapable of finding replacements, resulting in concern, anxiety and agitation in the long term. (Wang, Lee, Hua, 2015).

Continuous use of social media has its disadvantages or consequences to the user. The term continued use is used for users still using social media even knowing negative consequences while compulsive use is defined as using social media without awareness of the negative outcomes. Spending three or more hours can lead to poor mental health and disordered eating in young adults. Impulse controlled disorders may be due to excessive internet and virtual world usage. Work, academic productivity, and mental health can also be affected by addictive use of social media. An individual's mental health can be affected by lack of social support, resulting in depression and anxiety symptoms that people use SNSs for preventing loneliness and satisfying their social interaction needs to change their social mood as a way of running from daily life problems. (Andreassen et al., 2013; Chung et al., 2019; Hilliard & Parisi, 2020; Vannucci et al., 2017). The wellbeing, social functioning, sleep, academic and work performance and health can be affected by social media addiction and impulse control disorder. (Turel, Brevers, Bechara, 2018). Most addicted people can feel guilt or anxiety, impacting detrimentally on individual's lives, through introversion and social isolation. (Vannucci et al., 2017). Envy, depression, sleep loss, and anxiety developments were found to be due to excessive social media usage. (Chung et al., 2019; Baccarella et al., 2018). Vannucci et al, (2017). States that most anxiety disorders are accompanied with significant psychiatric and chronic diseases.

Social media addiction can be controlled if a person schedules the time on internet use on social media 30 minutes at night and one hour before sleep time; find new ways of socializing such as being a member of an organization, learning a new hobby for filling the spare time instead of mindlessly scrolling through newsfeed; the individual can also turn off notifications to concentrate on daily tasks; spending more time with friends' and family members in real life; thinking of social media as a threat, and using it for a while after first doing something productive; they should avoid posting everything about their achievements, have a break or holiday from social media through informing friends and telling them how they can reach through phone calls or family religious associates, deactivating or blocking any addictive sites; and getting help from an addiction counselor can be some ways of overcoming internet addiction. Another way is to avoid posting photographs or posts every day, and enjoying nature, surroundings and environment, meditation, and other forms of entertainment such as reading, visiting the library swimming, running, shopping etc., calling somebody if needed to be reached instead of sending social media messages, planning a new career change or learning a new skill. (Heston, 2019). After stopping social media addiction, more time and attention for other things, better focusing, better social connections and not much need for external validation can be beneficial results. (Campbell, 2019 Avison, 2020; Ayeni, 2019; Perspecti Counseling, 2020). Another way to control social addiction is turning the mobile phone off, setting it on flight mode or silent mode can also be self-controlled interventions. Not logging on to

SNSs while busy at work or school, leaving the smartphone at home, giving adequate breaks for visiting SNSs, modifying thought patterns, setting limits and reasonable goals, and committing to offline activities can be other self-help ways to decrease SNSs addiction. (Andreassen, 2015; Brevers and Turel, 2019). Kurniasih and Amriwijaya, (2018) suggested web Therapy which is the employment of web resources, e-books and e-journals and the reading of them in the treatment of mental and nervous diseases and disorders” is a self-help treatment method that can be used to overcome social media addiction problems. By talking with others through social media for relaxation which is both humorous and refreshing can be read to decrease anxiety. Sad and happy, laughable reading materials and stories can be shared online to solve problems. Interaction or communication through chatting are also types of information used by internet addicts for self-healing. (Klare, 2019; Ayeni 2019) also discussed ways to defeat a social media addiction through firstly acknowledging your addiction, reviewing a past post, setting priorities right, turning off all notifications, avoid posting everyday life experiences, limiting our social media usage and if necessary transferring our social media account to another person and decide to meet more people in real life. Finally, Pharmacological Interventions with medications are used to treat addictive people, according to Andreassen, (2015).

Methodology

A descriptive survey design was used for the study. 150 Diploma students made up the study’s population, and 100 of them from the Departments of Mass communication, Accountancy, Statistics, Computer science, and Computer engineering. The sample size for the study was 48, and purposive sampling technique was used. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data from students of the departments of the Polytechnic. The researcher gave the respondents the Questionnaire, Chi Square and descriptive analysis were used to analyse the results. The results are displayed in the table below;

Results

The findings of the study are presented in the following tables with explanations

Table 1: Gender of Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	25	52
Female	23	48
Total	48	100

The result in table 1 implies that the majority of the students under study were male.

Research Questions

This section discusses the findings of this study based on the research questions raised. The results are presented in Tables 2-8

Research Question 1: Do you use any of the social media platforms?

Table 2: Use of Social Media Platforms

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	46	96
No	2	4
Total	48	100

Table 2 shows implies that the majority of the students 46(96%) use social media platforms while 2(4%) don't use any of the social media platforms. This implies that the majority of the students use social media platforms. With the ease to which Internet-ready mobile devices, interested users can easily own and use smart devices. This has further increased the potential users of social media platforms, which is as simple as a download from any of the software stores.

Research Question 2: Which social media platforms do you use mostly?

Table 3: Social Media Platforms Mostly Used by the Students

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
WhatsApp	41	85
Facebook	29	60
YouTube	15	31
Snapchat	15	31
Instagram	10	21
Twitter	8	17
Others	1	2

Table 3 reveals that the majority of the students 41(85%) use WhatsApp, 29(60%) use Facebook, 15(31%) use YouTube and Snapchat respectively. 10(21%) use Instagram, 8(17%) use Twitter while 1(2%) use others outside the research listed social platforms. This implies that the majority of the students use WhatsApp and Facebook platforms mostly. This is not entirely strange, as research has shown Facebook and WhatsApp have the largest user base on the entire planet.

Research Question 3: Do you use social media platforms for sex related activities?

Table 4: Use of Social Media Platforms for Sex Related Activities

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	3	6
No	45	94
Total	48	100

Table 4 shows that the majority of the students 45(94%) don't use social media platforms for sex related activities while only 3(6%) use it for sex related activities. This implies that the majority of the students don't use social platforms for sex related activities. The higher responses in the negative may be due to the private nature of the question.

Research Question 4: How frequent do you use social media platforms?

Table 5: Frequency of the Use of Social Media Platforms

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very often	23	48
Often	20	42
Occasionally	5	8
Not at all	-	-

Table 5 reveals that the majority of the students 23(48%) use social media platforms very often, 20(42%) use it often while 5(8%) use it occasionally. A high amount of time spent on social platforms indicates an impulsiveness that is akin to addictive behaviour. From the responses, it shows a high addiction level to social media platforms.

Research Question 5: What are the reasons for using social media sites by students?

Table 6: Reasons for the Use of Social Media Platforms

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
For education	35	73
For communication	22	46
For pleasure and entertainment	21	44
Online dating	3	6
Gambling	1	2

Table 6 shows that the majority of the students 35(73%) use social media platforms for education, 22(46%) use it for communication, 21(44%) use it for pleasure and entertainment, 3(6%) use it for online dating while 1(2%) use it for gambling. This implies that the majority of the students use social platforms for education, communication and for pleasure and entertainment.

Research Question 6: Does the use of social media platforms affect your use of the library?

Table 7: Effects of the Use of Social Media Platforms on the Use of the Library

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	14	29
No	34	71
Total	48	100

Table 7 reveals that the use of social media platforms does not affect the majority 34(71%) of the students use of the library while 14(29%) agree that the use of social media platforms affect their use of the library. This implies that the use of social platforms does not affect majority of the students' use of the library.

Research Question 7: Are you addicted to social media platforms?

Table 8: Addiction to Social Media Platforms

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	2	4
No	46	96
Total	48	100

Table 8 shows that the majority of the students 46(96%) are not addicted to the use social media platforms while only 2(4%) of the students are addicted to social media. This indicates that the majority of the students claim not to be addicted to the use social platforms. However, time spent on their phones indicate otherwise as many were observed using their phones during class, in the library, and while walking.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Social media is not going away anytime soon, and the newer functionalities continue to spur and increase usage among different user groups. It will be wishful thinking to hope that social media addiction will sort itself out. The study concludes that social media is both beneficial to library users but at the same time library users should be careful not to be addicted to social media, thus becoming become social media addicts. It could have dire consequences to their physical and mental health, also it might lead to psychological and physical disorders. It can also cause poor reading habits that can affect their grades at school because it is time consuming. They can defeat social media Addiction through acknowledging their addiction, review past post, set priorities right, turn off all notifications, avoid posting everyday life experiences, limit their social media usage and transfer their social media account to another people. They should use their time in meaningful activities such as learning a new skill, reading and visit libraries so they can prosper educationally.

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